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Morphological Classification and Lexical-Semantic Features of Sports Terms and Lexemes in English and Uzbek Languages

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Annotation: This article investigates the morphological classification and lexical-semantic features of sports terms and lexemes in English and Uzbek languages. It examines sports terminology from both structural and functional perspectives, focusing on how lexical units are organized according to parts of speech and semantic roles. The study identifies the proportion of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs within sports terminology and highlights their functional distribution in both languages. In addition, the research analyzes terminological combinations and their semantic integrity, as well as their role in expressing complex sports concepts. The comparative analysis reveals both isomorphic and allomorphic features in term formation, particularly in morphological processes such as affixation and compounding. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of sports discourse and terminological system organization in typologically different languages.

Keywords: morphological classification, lexical-semantic features, sports terminology, terminological combinations, word formation processes, comparative linguistics, english sports lexemes, uzbek sports terminology.

Introduction. Sports terminology represents a dynamic linguistic subsystem that evolves alongside the development of physical education and competitive sports. The emergence of new sports disciplines has led to the formation of specialized terminological systems characterized by structural complexity and semantic diversity. In English and Uzbek languages, sports lexemes function not only as naming units but also as indicators of actions, processes, and professional roles within sports activities. The study of such terminology is essential for understanding how different languages conceptualize and structure sports-related knowledge. This article explores the morphological and lexical-semantic aspects of sports terms, emphasizing their classification according to parts of speech and their functional distribution in discourse.

Literature review. R. I. Komarova and S. Khalilova emphasize that the limited number of lexical units expressing a specific concept leads to the repeated use of the same words, which in turn causes a number of semantic ambiguities in the meaning of terms(1). Indeed, the need to clarify meaning and eliminate semantic ambiguity further increases the demand for terminological combinations, which serve as a convenient means of expressing complex concepts in a concise form. Terminological

combinations are higher-level units that govern lower-level linguistic units. Terminological combinations also express genus-species relations between concepts. As a general rule, they may consist of two, three, or more components(2). A term can be associated with a single concept within a specific field. However, the situation in which a word encapsulates only one concept is relatively rare, and in such cases we refer to the term in its 'pure' sense. This is because a pure term must satisfy two main criteria: it must belong to only one terminological system and express only one specific concept. Pure terms typically arise in the process of purposeful and conscious activity of specialists working within a narrow field of knowledge. The main feature of a terminological combination is explained by its ability to express a single, clearly defined concept. Functionally and semantically, it is manifested within a system of terms that denote concepts restricted to a particular conceptual field.

Another distinctive feature of terminological combinations is their semantic integrity. The semantic wholeness of a word combination is reflected in idiomaticity, which is understood as 'the non-compositionality of meaning from the meanings of its constituent parts in the overall formation of language(3). Although a term is relatively free in terms of its field of use, it is strictly governed by the rules of the language. In other words, the use of a term in other domains is directly related to its semantic properties. Accordingly, if word combinations extend beyond the boundaries of the conceptual group under study, they are regarded as contextually formed units. Such units are created in a specific moment of speech, depending on the communicative situation, and exist only temporarily. An important structural component of such free combinations is a particular word - a term.

Thus, terminological combinations, on the one hand, are characterized by their functional-semantic integrity, while on the other hand, their semantic structure contains more information than that derived from the individually understood associative components(4). The following examples of such terminological combinations in English are appropriate to consider.

to start from scratch - to gain no benefit (to start from zero);
straight header - "swallow" (a body position resembling a flying bird) (swimming);
straight – not bent or curved; header - a fall or jump into water (a dive) in which the head enters the water before the feet (to dive headfirst) (5). It should be particularly noted that terminological combinations can be classified into several types according to their structural and semantic features. In this sense, based on the number of components in their structure, it is appropriate to classify English and Uzbek sports-related multi-word terms in the following way.

When studying sports-related terms and lexemes in English and Uzbek languages, we attempted to show the proportion of collected terms and lexemes in general sports terminology according to their affiliation with parts of speech. We consider it necessary to classify them into the following groups based on their morphological usage.

✓ Sports-related terms and lexemes belonging to the noun category in English and Uzbek. Their share in sports terminology constitutes approximately 60 percent. The following terms and lexemes can be cited as examples.

In English: helmet - protective headgear; sit-back; squatting - a training exercise involving sitting and standing; station - an athlete's starting position in a competition; stand-off - a draw; spurt - a sudden burst of effort (e.g. in weightlifting or shot put); stayer - a long-distance runner; steeplechaser - an athlete competing in steeplechase (running over obstacles); In Uzbek: game, elephant, chessboard, ship, striker, defender, goalkeeper, athlete, handball, hockey, surfing, kayak, sprinter, cyclist, helmet, sprinter, etc.

✓ The overall proportion of sports terms and lexemes belonging to the verb category in English and Uzbek sports terminology accounts for 30 percent. The following lexical units can be cited as examples.

In English: *to start* - to begin; *to seed* - to accelerate/advance (context-dependent usage); *to shag* - to chase the ball, etc; *to shy* - (of a horse) to shy or startle and jump aside; *to slice* - in tennis or golf, a shot that deviates from a straight trajectory; an incorrect strike of the ball; etc. In Uzbek: *boshlamoq* (to start), *start bermoq* (to give the start), *tugatmoq* (to finish), *yugurmoq* (to run), *sakramoq* (to jump), *mo'ljalga tekkizmoq* (to hit the target), *nishonni urmoq* (to hit the mark), *g'alaba qozonmoq* (to win), *yutqazmoq* (to lose), *mag'lubiyatga uchramoq* (to suffer defeat), *g'alabani saqlab qolmoq* (to maintain victory), *gol urmoq* (to score a goal), *himoya qilmoq* (to defend), *hujum qilmoq* (to attack), etc.

✓ The overall proportion of adjectives in English and Uzbek sports terminological units accounts for 5 percent. The following lexical units can be given as examples.

In English: *sick* - not feeling well; *scientific* - highly skilled, possessing advanced technique; *off-track* - outside the running lane/track; *off* - the left side of the field (in cricket terminology); *overall* - absolute; *overhand* - an overhead (high) pass or throw, etc. In Uzbek: *mohir* (skilled), *ayyorona* (cunning), *qo'qqisdan* (sudden), *kasal* (sick), *jarohatlangan* (injured), *diskvalifikatsiya qilingan* (disqualified), *chetlashtirilgan* (excluded), *professional* (professional), *yuqori ko'rsatkichga ega* (high-performing), *tezkor* (fast), *shiddatli* (intense), *hujumkor* (offensive), *darvozaga yo'naltirilgan* (goal-oriented), *play-off* (play-off stage), etc.

✓ The overall proportion of adverbs in English and Uzbek sports terminological units accounts for 5 percent. These lexical units include the following examples.

In English: *out* — out (the ball is out of play); *in* — in form/fit, etc. In Uzbek: *mohirona* (skillfully), *ayyorona* (cunningly), *qo'qqisdan* (suddenly), *professional* (professionally), *tezkor* (quickly), *shiddatli* (vigorously), *hujumkor* (offensively), etc.

In English and Uzbek sports-related terminology and lexemes, it is possible to classify the material collected for analysis into the following lexical-semantic groups.

- Terminological lexemes denoting sports-related events, processes, and actions in English and Uzbek languages.

For example, in English: *body checking* - body check (physical inspection/contact action); *hand pass* - hand pass (to pass the ball by hand); *to clear the puck* - to clear the puck (to move it away from the penalty area); *face-off* - puck drop to start play; *to finish a check* - to complete a body check; *to shadow* - to closely follow an opponent; *top stroke* - a high shot; *breakout* - to break through defensive pressure, etc. In Uzbek: *uzatma* (pass), *xizmat tekshiruvi* (service check), *(suvga) sho'ng'imoq* (to dive), *to'pni uzatmoq / pas bermoq* (to pass the ball), *ta'qib qilmoq* (to pursue), *konkur* (horse jumping over obstacles), *erkin zarba* (free kick), *hujum* (attack), *manëvr/finte qilmoq* (to feint), *to'siqlar osha yugurmoq* (to run over obstacles), *pressing*, *straïk* (strike), etc.

- Terminological lexemes in English and Uzbek languages indicating the type of sport or professional affiliation of athletes .

In English: *billiard player* - billiards player; *underwater swimmer* - underwater swimmer; *diver* - diver (scuba diver); *judge* - judge (official); *referee* - referee (chief official in sports competitions); *hang glider pilot* - hang glider pilot; *pilot* - pilot; *road racer* - road racer; *racing cyclist* - cyclist; *racing motorcyclist* - motorcycle racer; *coach* - coach; *handball player* - handball player; *hockey player* - hockey player. *Diver* - a person who dives, especially one who works at the bottom of the sea in special protective clothing with an air supply - a person operating underwater in a special suit supplied with air. *Coach* - a person who trains sportsmen and sportswomen for games, competitions, etc. - a specialist responsible for preparing athletes for competitions(6). In Uzbek, terminological lexemes indicating athletes' sports affiliation include: *billiardchi* (billiards player), *suzuvchi* (swimmer), *g'avvos* (diver), *hakam* (referee/judge), *pilot* (pilot), *velopoygach* (cyclist), *murabbiy* (coach), *gandbolchi* (handball player), *xokkeychi* (hockey player), *basketbolchi* (basketball player), *futbolchi* (football player), *voleybolchi* (volleyball player), *futzalchi* (futsal player), *kurashchi* (wrestler), *bokschi* (boxer), *tennisch* (tennis player), *badmintonchi* (badminton player), *atlet* (athlete), *gimnast* (gymnast), *kickbokschi* (kickboxer), *karatechi* (karate practitioner), *dzyudochi* (judoka), *chang'ichi* (skier), etc. These can be illustrated by the following example. For instance: **Trainer** (from English *trainer* - *train* - to teach, to coach) - a specialist responsible for guiding and supervising athletes preparation in a specific sport. Example: *the coach of a football team*(7).

Conclusion. The analysis demonstrates that sports terminology in English and Uzbek languages is characterized by both shared and language-specific features. Nouns constitute the dominant group of sports lexemes, followed by verbs, adjectives, and adverbs, reflecting similar functional distributions in both languages. However, differences arise due to typological distinctions, particularly the analytical structure of English and the synthetic nature of Uzbek. The study also confirms that terminological combinations play a crucial role in expressing complex sports concepts with semantic precision and structural coherence. Overall, the research highlights the systematic organization of sports terminology and emphasizes the importance of its continuous linguistic analysis and standardization across languages.

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